

Multiscale modeling of additively manufactured short fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer composites

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Motivation

- Significant gaps exist between the performance, environmental and economic targets, and current design and manufacturing approaches for polymer composites
- Lack of detailed understanding of influence of material architecture, process methods and parameters on the microstructure evolution and product performance

Build an AI-enabled inverse design platform for integrated material-manufacturing design of advanced polymer composites

Objectives

- Develop a **computational framework** to reveal the material-process-microstructure-performance (**MP2**) **relationship** for thermoplastic composites across various length scales and time scales
- Develop microscale/mesoscale models that serve as a bridge between multi-physics-based nanoscale models and macroscale material models
- Generate data for the **training/validation of the AI models**, to develop an AI-enabled inverse design platform for integrated material-manufacturing design of advanced polymer composites.

Fused deposition modeling (FDM) overview

Micro-CT showing porosity

Raster patterns

Scanning Electron Micrograph

AM material testing: CF-Nylon

Anisotropy of CF-Nylon

- XY direction shows stiffest and strongest properties due to 0-90 fiber orientation
- XZ direction is weakest due to inter-layer bond being subjected to max. shear stress

Orthogonal raster

Raster angle
0 and 90
degrees

Raster angle
-45 and +45
degrees

→
Loading direction

Testing setup with DIC strain measurement

AM material testing

Tension-compression asymmetry of CF-Nylon

- Elastic behavior is identical between tension and compression
- Plastic behavior is different in tension and compression resulting from two competing

Uniaxial Tension vs. Compression

Void expansion/closure

Fiber rotation in X direction

Microstructure measurement

- Meso-scale **porosity** or voids result from the FDM process and **affect macroscopic material properties**
- Micro-CT imaging used to “measure” the internal structure of CF-Nylon
- Reconstructed 3D structure shows 8.96 % void fraction

Micro tomograms

Reconstructed 3D structure of voids

Microstructure reconstruction

• Microstructure measurement and reconstruction

µCT Image histogram

Histogram normalization

• Method 1: Actual microstructure

- Large # of elements- High computational cost
- May vary significantly within samples

3D microstructure reconstruction

AM-built polymer composite (green) and voids (red)

Void distribution

• Method 2: Synthetic microstructure

- Based on statistical information
- Parameterized model
- Computational efficiency

Synthetic microstructure

Actual and synthetic microstructures

FE simulations on actual and synthetic microstructure show similar results.
Ideal synthetic microstructure is representative.

Direction	Model (RVE size mm/element size μm)			
	(A) Ideal 9% void (1.5/ Tetrahedral 40)	(B) Actual 9.5% void* (1/ Hexahedral 40)	(C) Actual 9.5% void* (1/ Hexahedral 40)	(D) Actual 9.3% void* (1/ Hexahedral 20)
X	1545	1551	1550	1596
Z	1250	1385	1384	1341

Local material modeling

Homogenization of microstructure

Transversely isotropic elasticity

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_1} & \frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & \frac{1}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{13}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{13}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu_{12})}{E_1} \end{bmatrix}$$

Hill 1948 yield function for transversely isotropic material

$$F(\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + G(\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2 + H(\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + 2L\sigma_{yz}^2 + 2M\sigma_{zx}^2 + 2N\sigma_{xy}^2 = \bar{\sigma}^2$$

$$F = G = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_z} \right)^2$$

$$H = \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_x} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_z} \right)^2$$

$$N = 2 \left[\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_{xy}} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_z} \right)^2 \right] \quad N = H + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_x} \right)^2$$

$$L = M = 2 \left[\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_{xz}} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{S_x} \right)^2 \right]$$

Iterative calibration using fmincon

$$\min_x f(x) \text{ such that } \begin{cases} c(x) \leq 0 \\ ceq(x) = 0 \\ A \cdot x \leq b \\ Aeq \cdot x = beq \\ lb \leq x \leq ub, \end{cases}$$

$$x = [S_{11}, S_{33}, S_{12}, S_{13}, S_{44}]$$

FE simulations of UT on RVE along 4 directions

$$f(x) = err = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \left((E_x^{exp} - E_x^{sim})^2 + (E_z^{exp} - E_z^{sim})^2 + \dots \right)}$$

Experimental data

$$\begin{matrix} E_x(E_y), E_z, E_{xy} (45 \text{ deg}) \\ \nu_{xy}, \nu_{xz}(\nu_{yz}), \nu (45 \text{ deg}) \end{matrix}$$

Mesoscale modeling results: Elastic properties

Elastic moduli prediction

Model	Voids	Material model	Resultant RVE
—	No	Isotropic	Isotropic material
A	Yes	Isotropic	Orthotropic material due to isolated effect of voids
B	No	Transversely isotropic	Orthotropic material due to isolated effect of fibers
C	yes	Transversely isotropic	Orthotropic material due to combined effect of voids and fibers

- Model A: Effect of porosity only
- Model B: Effect of local anisotropy only
- Model C: Effect of porosity + local anisotropy combined

Mesoscale modeling results: Plastic behavior

Plastic anisotropy prediction

Hill's 1948 yield function

$$F(\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + G(\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2 + H(\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + 2L\sigma_{yz}^2 + 2M\sigma_{zx}^2 + 2N\sigma_{xy}^2 = \bar{\sigma}^2$$

	YS [MPa]			
Dir.	X	Z	XY	XZ
Exp	17.55	25.2	36	16
Sim	17.3	24.7	36.77	17.25
Error (%)	-1.4	-1.9	2.1	7.8

Hill's 1948 yield function coefficients

F	G	H	L	M	N
0.5	0.5	1.28	3.06	4.96	4.96

Internal self-contact

Contact pressure

Mesoscale modeling results: Tension-compression asymmetry

Tension-compression asymmetry prediction

Ongoing and future work

- Account for anisotropic hardening
- Implement damage model for matrix
- Account for fiber-matrix interaction with interfacial damage

GTN (Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman) model

$$\Phi^*(\sigma, \bar{\epsilon}_M, f^*) = \left(\frac{f_Y(\sigma)}{\bar{\sigma}_M} \right)^2 + 2f^*q_1 \cosh\left(\frac{3q_2p}{2\bar{\sigma}_M} \right) - (1 + q_3f^{*2}) = 0$$

Mesoscale modeling results: Residual stress

AM process modeling

- Thermomechanical simulation of the AM process captures effect of process parameters
- AM process simulation predicts resultant residual stresses
- Residual stresses may affect mechanical properties of components
- Effect of individual raster shapes and voids
 - Commercial AM process simulation tools don't allow custom cross-section shape for individual printed tracks.
 - Default rectangular cross-section ignores mesoscale voids and their effect on temperature/stress distribution
 - Novel methodology developed here can account for track shapes without dedicated user subroutine

Conclusions and Future works

- The meso-scale modeling methodology developed in this study can account for the effect of **process-induced microstructure** on the **macroscopic elasto-plastic properties**.
- Future work includes implementation of **damage models** to capture the **anisotropic hardening** and **asymmetry between tension and compression** more accurately.
- Effect of **residual stress** from **AM** process on the material behavior will be captured and integrated with RVE model.
- Periodic boundary conditions will be applied to unit cell-based synthetic microstructures to improve computational efficiency and minimize the influence of surface boundary conditions.
- The effects of raster shape and the spatially non-uniform distribution of voids will be evaluated.

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